

Sources of dual resistance to whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) and green leafhopper (GLH)

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We evaluated 100 rice accessions from the 1985 International Rice Whitebacked Planthopper Nursery for resistance to WBPH *Sogatella furcifera* under greenhouse conditions; 15 accessions were identified as resistant. The WBPH-resistant varieties were further evaluated for resistance to GLH *Nephotettix virescens*, using the standard seedbox screening test.

Pregerminated seeds were sown in 60- × 40- × 10-cm seedboxes. Ptb 33 was the resistant check and TN1 the susceptible check. Each accession was replicated five times for each insect species. Seedlings were infested with 8 2d-instar nymphs of WBPH and 5 2d-instar nymphs of GLH/seedling 7 d after sowing. Damage was rated using the *Standard evaluation system for rice* when 90-100% of TN1 plants had died.

All 15 accessions were resistant to WBPH and to GLH (see table). □

Resistance of selected rice accessions to WBPH and GLH. Greenhouse, TNAU, Coimbatore, India, 1985.

Rice accession	Damage rating ^a	
	WBPH	GLH
Chempan	1 a	1 a
Chempan pandi	3 b	1 a
Horonamawee	1 a	1 a
IR9852-22-3	1 a	1 a
IR13427-40-2-3-3	1 a	1 a
IR13429-196-1	1 a	1 a
IR13475-7-3-2	1 a	1 a
IR15429-268-1-2-1	3 b	1 a
IR15527-21-2-3	3 b	1 a
IR15529-256-1	3 b	1 a
IR15795-151-2-3-2-2	1 a	1 a
IR28154-101-3-2	1 a	1 a
Podiwi A8	3 b	1 a
Valsara Champara	1 a	1 a
Sufaida 172	1 a	1 a
Ptb 33 (resistant check)	1 a	1 a
TN1 (susceptible check)	9 c	9 b

^aMean of 5 replications. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by Duncan's multiple range test.

Yield of gall midge (GM)-resistant rice varieties after early pulse crop at Hyderabad

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Yields of GM-resistant rices WGL 20506, WGL 23022, and WGL 16145 and cultivar Surekha following a green manure crop were examined. An early pulse crop was harvested in early Aug. The trial compared broadcasting sprouted seed and transplanting 30-d-old seedlings. Sowing was on 1 Aug and 16 Aug. Seed rate for broadcasting was 120 kg/ha, spacing for transplanting was 10 × 10 cm. Recommended fertilizer was 80-22 kg NP/ha. N was applied in three splits, all the P was applied basally.

Yield of promising GM-resistant rices following a green manure crop on 2 planting dates, Hyderabad, India.^a

Cultivar	Yield (t/ha)			
	2 Aug planting		16 Aug planting	
	BC	TP	BC	TP
WGL 20506	3.5	3.5	3.6	3.3
WGL 23022	3.6	4.0	3.3	3.9
WGL 16145	3.3	5.0	2.4	4.4
Surekha	3.5	5.0	2.7	4.4
Mean yield	3.6	4.4	3.0	4.0

^aBC = broadcast, TP = transplanted.

Transplanted crops yielded higher than broadcast crops (see table). Increases were 34.7% in WGL 16145 and 30.2% in Surekha in the first planting and 16.5% in WGL 23022, 40.5% in WGL 16145, and 38.8% in Surekha in the second planting. □

Resistance of selected *Oryza sativa* and *O. brachyantha* cultivars to the rice leaffolder (LF)

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Mass screening in the IRRI greenhouse has yielded cultivars with resistance or moderate resistance to the LF *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* Guenée. Oviposition, larval survival, and host preference were studied on three

resistant wild rices and five resistant cultivars.

One-month-old seedlings were planted in 5-cm-diam clay pots at 5 plants/pot per cultivar in a randomized complete block design with 5 replications. For the oviposition treatment, each replication was enclosed in a fiberglass net and 50 pairs of newly emerged adults were introduced. Eggs laid were counted after 3 d.

For larval survival measurement,

Table 1. Larval survival and oviposition preference of rice LF on *Oryza brachyantha* and *O. sativa* cultivars.^a IRRI, 1986.

<i>Oryza</i> spp.	Accession no.	Larval survival (%)	Oviposition preference
<i>O. brachyantha</i>	101232	2 a	71 a
<i>O. brachyantha</i>	101233	14 a	63 a
<i>O. brachyantha</i>	101234	10 a	80 a
<i>O. sativa</i>			
Darukasail	45493	56 bc	128 b
Kamalbhog	49020	52 bc	176 c
Choorapundy	48529	38 b	131 b
TKM6	237	44 bc	172 c
TN1	105	64 c	227 d

^aAv of 5 replications. n = 10. Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different (P = 0.05) by DMRT.

pots were infested with two 1st-instar larvae/tiller and enclosed in mylar film cages. Surviving larvae were determined 17 d after infestation.

To study host preference, 15-cm-diam petri dishes were divided into 6 areas. Three leaf pieces of each variety tested and 3 control leaf cuts were placed in alternate areas and 24 1st-instar larvae were placed in the center. Larvae settling on each leaf piece were counted at 24 h. Five replications were made.

O. brachyantha were more resistant than the *O. sativa* cultivars; fewer eggs were laid on them and fewer larvae survived (Table 1). Fewer larvae also settled on the wild rice leaves (Table 2).

Wild rices belonging to the *O. brachyantha* group have narrow, short leaves; *O. sativa* varieties have long, and broad leaves. Correlation of plant

Table 2. Attraction of rice LF larvae to *Oryza brachyantha* and *O. sativa* cultivars.^a IRRI, 1986.

<i>Oryza</i> spp.	Accession no.	Feeding preference (no. larvae/arena) ^b	Difference ^c
<i>O. brachyantha</i>	101232	8	56 **
	TN1	64	
<i>O. brachyantha</i>	101233	15	32 **
	TN1	47	
<i>O. brachyantha</i>	101234	16	42 **
	TN1	58	
<i>O. sativa</i>	45493	32	21 *
	TN1	59	
Kamalbhog	49020	34	27 *
	TN1	61	
Choorapundy	49529	34	17 *
	TN1	51	
TKM6	237	39	19 *
	TN1	58	

^a Av of 5 replications. n = 24. ^b Reading taken at 24 h. ^c Level of significance: ** = 0.01, * = 0.05. TN1 is the susceptible check.

characters and LF infestation showed that cultivars with longer, broader leaves had more damage. These

cultivars' leaves may have made folding easier, providing larger feeding areas. □

Green leafhopper (GLH) resistance in wild rices

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We evaluated 24 wild rices for resistance to GLH *Nephotettix virescens* under greenhouse conditions by the standard seedbox screening. Pregerminated seeds were sown in 60- × 40- × 10-cm seedboxes with resistant check Ptb 33 and susceptible check TN1. Each accession had five replications.

Seedlings were infested with 5 2d-instar nymphs/seedling 7 d after sowing. Damage was rated when 90-100% of susceptible TN1 seedlings died.

Sixteen wild rices were resistant, four were moderately resistant, and four were susceptible to *N. virescens* (see table). □

Reaction of wild rices to *Nephotettix virescens* in seedbox screening, TNAU, Coimbatore, India, 1985-86.

Species	Origin	IRRI acc. no.	Damage rating ^a
<i>Oryza latifolia</i>	Panama	100966	1 a
<i>O. punctata</i>	Ghana	101409	1 a
<i>O. nivara</i>	India	101510	1 a
<i>O. australiensis</i>	Australia	103318	1 a
<i>O. nivara</i>	Sri Lanka	103419	1 a
<i>O. glaberrima</i>	Senegal	103438	1 a
<i>O. rufipogon</i>	Venezuela	103810	1 a
<i>O. sativalo/O. spontanea</i>	Bangladesh	103826	1 a
<i>O. nivara</i>	Bangladesh	103835	1 a
<i>O. rufipogon</i>	Bangladesh	103844	1 a
<i>O. perennis</i>	India	103846	1 a
<i>O. perennis</i>	India	103848	1 a
<i>O. glaberrima</i>	Senegal	103439	3 b
<i>O. glaberrima</i>	Senegal	103443	3 b
<i>O. sativalo/O. spontanea</i>	Bangladesh	103831	3 b
<i>O. perennis</i>	India	103845	3 b
<i>O. nivara</i>	Australia	101466	5 c
<i>O. glaberrima</i>	Senegal	103437	5 c
<i>O. glaberrima</i>	Senegal	103488	5 c
<i>O. rufipogon/O. nivara</i>	Burma	103796	5 c
<i>O. minuta</i>	Philippines	101132	7 d
<i>O. eichingeri</i>	Tanzania	101171	7 d
<i>O. nivara/O. sativa</i>	Sri Lanka	103791	7 d
<i>O. nivara</i>	Bangladesh	103836	9 e
Ptb 33 (resistant check)			1 a
TN1 (susceptible check)			9 e

^a Mean of 5 replications. Damage rating based on 0-9 scale. Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by Duncan's multiple range test.

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